

Research on seafood: Distribution and origin

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Abstract

Seafood, as the word implies, is basically sea animals that are being served as food. Being actively eaten as a significant part of the human diet, people either search for them in the ocean or they cultivate them in mass numbers. The question is raised in where the origins of these sea products are? Which farm they came from, or which regions in the oceans are they found in. I took samples of shellfish and crustaceans to amplify the mitochondrial COI DNA fragments. These DNA fragments are then used for species identification. As many as 7 out of the 13 specimens were successfully identified, and most of the species belong to the class Bivalvia. Others respectively belonged to the Gastropoda and Crustacea. Some of the specimens were identified to be similar species with differences spotted in morphological features. Analysis of geographical distribution of these identified species is now underway and is expected to yield further information on the possible geographic origin of these seafood species.

1. Introduction

Seafood is an important food source to human society. As the name implied, seafood is basically any animal from the ocean that could be served as food. This includes oyster, crab, shrimp, lobsters, clam, octopus, squid, mussel, tuna, salmon, scallop, and many others. These food sources have two benefits to humans. First, they are essential nutrient source for human because they are high in protein, vitamin, and mineral levels while low in fat, sodium, and cholesterol levels [1]. Second, they are a great economical benefit towards the human society because there are a wide variety of industries associated with seafood production and trade could drive the economy forward by earning billions annually [2].

However, seafood industries have connections all around the world, so not all seafood are produced locally, which means that the seafoods are imported and exported between different countries. They will have to be transported by the means of ocean and air traveling such as shipping and air freight. Consequentially, during the transportation, Carbon

dioxide could be emitted into the environment. Due to carbon dioxide's greenhouse gas properties, it could contribute to environmental problems such as global warming and air pollution. Therefore, it is important to investigate seafood trade by studying the origins of seafood sold in local markets.

Shenzhen is a highly developed coastal urban city. Seafood consumption is common among the locals, so it is important to investigate the origins of seafood in order to understand the carbon emission brought by consuming seafood. In this study, I used PCR methods to trace the original distribution of the seafood sold in local markets. Thus, they could determine if the seafoods are produced locally or overseas in order to compare their carbon emission levels.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sampling

Samples were bought at Xiang Mei Market's seafood section on Jin Tian Road. There are a total of 17 species such as crustaceans, bivalves, and gastropods, including a type of barnacle found on a crustacean. The samples were collected in two separate days. Photos with IDs and scale bars of the first 9 specimens were immediately taken. They were then stored overnight in a glass beaker with 99.8% ethanol before further processing. The second 9 specimens were first killed with the 99.8% ethanol, and pictures were then taken.

2.2. DNA extraction

Next, the preserved samples were dissected. Muscle tissues were collected from the samples, and roe was collected from one of the crustaceans (the crab). Each piece of tissue was ground with glass homogenizer and transferred into 2 mL centrifuge tubes. DNA extraction was conducted using

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the Biospin (Biospin, Beijing, China) Marine Animal Genomic DNA Extraction Kit. Lysis solution, which is 600 μL of FL Buffer and 10 μL of PK solution, was added to the ground samples. The samples were then incubated and stirred in the 56°C water bath for around 3 hours.

After cell lysis, the samples were centrifuged with 14000g for 3 minutes. 500 μL of supernatant was transferred into another 2 mL centrifuge tube, and 700 μL of Binding Buffer and 300 μL of anhydrous ethanol were mixed with it. 750 μL of the supernatant solution was then transferred into the spin columns for 1 minute of centrifuge under 10000g, and the waste fluid was removed. This process was repeated once. Next, 500 μL of PW Buffer was added to each spin column before going through 10000g of centrifuge for 30 seconds. 600 μL of Wash Buffer was added into the spin columns and centrifuged for 30 seconds under 10000g. This process was also repeated once. After the removal of the waste fluid, the spin columns were again centrifuged under 10000g for 1 minute and were transferred to new 1.5 μL centrifuge tubes. Finally, 50 μL of distilled water was added to the spin columns to wash the DNA off by centrifuging them again. PCR amplification

The fragment of DNA amplified was the mitochondrial gene encoding cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI). First the concentration of the extracted DNA was measured by nanodrop device (Miulab, Hangzhou, China). Then, 1 μL from the each of the two primers,

LCO1490

(5'-GGTCAACAAATCATAAAGATATTGG-3')

and HCO2198

(5'-TAAACTTCAGGGTGACCAAAAAATCA-3'),

were mixed with 500ng of DNA template solution and 10 μL of Phanta Master Mix (P525-AA) from Vazyme. ddH₂O was added to the primer-DNA mixture to yield a final volume of 20 μL for the PCR reaction. The PCR process was as follows: 4 min at 94 °C, 30 cycles of 30 s at 94 °C, 30 s at 45 °C, 30 s at 72 °C, and 7 min at 72 °C. The product of PCR amplification was checked by electrophoresis to check for the correct size of the product band.

2.3. Data analysis

DNA sequences were tested by NCBI Blast using the Nucleotide BLAST function. The results with a per indent and query of above 95% were accepted, and the name of the species were recorded.

3. Results

In total, we collected 12 bivalve specimens, 3 gastropod specimens, and 3 crustacean specimens. Figure 1 showing the pie chart. I predicted that these specimens likely contain 17 species, as some specimens may be the same species based on their morphology. Figure 2 shows the representative photos of specimens. According to Figure 1, I believe

that the Futian MeiLin seafood market is mainly selling bivalves. Figure 3, MeiLin seafood market sampling site.

From the 18 specimens, I performed DNA extraction, PCR amplification of COI gene fragment, and then DNA sequencing, in order to identify the species identity of each specimen. Out of 18 specimens, the COI fragments of 12 specimens was successfully sequenced and used for species identification. For the most bivalve specimens, I identified 7 samples (FM-1, FM-3, FM-4, FM-5, FM-16, FM-17, and FM-23); these specimens covered 6 families within the class Bivalvia, including Mytilidae, Veneridae, Ostreidae, Pharidae, Solenidae, and Pinnidae. For the 3 crustacean specimens [there are two barnacle species (FM-24) *Conchoderma hunteri*, and *Octolasmis warwickii* collected from FM-22, a crab], *Thalamita sima* (FM-22) belongs to the Portunidae family, *Conchoderma hunteri* belongs to the Lepadidae family, and *Octolasmis warwickii* belongs to the Poecilasmatidae family. For the last 3 Gastropoda specimens, there are 2 *Neptunea* species (FM-19, FM-20) belonging to the family of Buccinidae, and *Babylonia lutosa* (FM-8) belonging to the Babyloniidae family.

Xiangmei Fishmarket seafood components

Figure 1. Futian MeiLin seafood market pie chart

4. Discussion

Through online research, I found the geological distribution of the specimens. Most of the species are from Indo-Pacific area, including the *Perna viridis*, *Meretrix* sp., *Paphia undulata*, *Babylonia lutosa*, *Solen* sp., *Thalamita sima*, *Atrina pectinata*, *Conchoderma hunteri*, and *Octolasmis warwickii* [(FM-1, FM-3, FM-5, FM-8, FM-17, FM-22, FM-23, FM-24 (two species)] (Shown on Table 1). Since the location covers the South China Sea coastline, the specimens could be cultivated and harvested in local regions. Some species are not from local areas, such as *Neptunea* sp. which belongs to West Atlantic Ocean area. The species might have been harvested in the Atlantic Ocean and then imported into China, or *Neptunea* species might have been brought into local areas to cultivate and harvest.

From an environmentally friendly perspective, consumers should keep track of the carbon footprint they left behind. The Indo-pacific seafoods from Xiang Mei fish market are

Figure 2. Photo of specimens collected from Futian MeiLin seafood market; all scales are 1 cm. **a.** FM-1, **b.** FM-3, **c.** FM-4, **d.** FM-5, **e.** FM-6(11), **f.** FM-9(12), **g.** FM-7(13), **h.** FM-16, **i.** FM-8(14), **j.** FM-17, **k.** FM-21, **l.** FM-18, **m.** FM-19, **n.** FM-23, **o.** FM-24, **p.** FM-20, **q.** FM-22.

collected from local regions, so they produce relatively low carbon emission. On the other hand, *Neptunea* sp. might

be imported through trade from the Atlantic Ocean. This suggests that the transportation methods such as shipping

Figure 3. Futian MeiLin seafood market

could produce more carbon emission than those collected from local regions, which could cause harm to the environment. However, evidence show that one of *Neptunea* sp. was distributed in Yellow Sea and Bohai [12]. For instance, *Neptunea cumingii* is cultivated along the Northern China coast, which is the main economically important shellfish in that region [13]. Compared to *Thalamita sima* crab that is caught locally, the shipping of *Neptunea cumingii* from northern China to Shenzhen could produce more carbon emission.

I detected two species of barnacle attached to the body of *Thalamita sima* crab, *Conchoderma hunteri* and *Octolasmis warwickii*. From an ecological perspective, if the two species of barnacle were brought along the shell of the crab *Thalamita sima* to other sea areas, they might release their larvae in those water bodies. For instance, another type of barnacle, *Amphibalanus reticulatus* originated in Indo-pacific regions, but the species was introduced to the Eastern Pacific, both sides of the Atlantic Ocean, and the Eastern Mediterranean. It was proven to be competing with other barnacles for living space [14]. Thus, there is a possibility for the larvae of *Conchoderma hunteri* and *Octolasmis warwickii* to settle and invade other barnacle species.

In conclusion, most of the seafood sold in Shenzhen Meilin fish market came from local sources, but some species might be imported from the Northern China. This means that most of the seafood came from Asia, suggesting that consumption of seafood bought from the market could pro-

duce a relatively low carbon emission compared to consuming imported seafood.

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Table 1. The successful identified specimen with their distribution.

sample ID	Species confirmed by COI	Geographical distribution	References
FM-1 FM-2	<i>Perna viridis</i>	Indian coast and throughout the Indo-Pacific	[3]
FM-3	<i>Meretrix</i> sp.	Indo-West Pacific: from East Africa to the Philippines; north to Japan and south to Indonesia.	[4]
FM-4	<i>Crassostrea sikamea</i>	Indo-West Pacific from the north-western Indian Ocean, including the Red Sea, to Papua New Guinea, north to Japan and south to New South Wales	[5]
FM-5	<i>Paphia undulata</i>		
FM-6 FM-7 FM-8 FM-9 FM-10 FM-11 FM-12 FM-13 FM-14 FM-15	<i>Babylonia lutosa</i>	Indo-West Pacific.	[6]
FM-16 FM-17 FM-18	<i>Sinonovacula rivularis</i> <i>Solen</i> sp.	Indonesia, dampier archipelago	[7]
FM-19	<i>Neptunea</i> sp.	Western Atlantic Ocean, Northeast Pacific and the Arctic: Alaska, Canada, USA. Subtropical to polar. North Atlantic and adjacent Arctic seas and are conspicuous among Pliocene and Pleistocene molluscs in the Icelandic, North Sea, and western Mediterranean basins.	[8]
FM-20 FM-21	<i>Neptunea</i> sp.		
FM-22	<i>Thalamita sima</i>	From Indian Ocean extends to Western Pacific and Australia	[9]
FM-23	<i>Atrina pectinata</i>	Mediterranean and Indo-West Pacific: from southeast Africa to Melanesia and New Zealand; north to Japan and south to New South Wales. Tropical to subtropical.	[10]
FM-24	<i>Conchoderma hunteri</i> , <i>Octolasmis warwickii</i>	1. Pacific and Indian Ocean 2. Indo-West Pacific, Indian Ocean to South Africa, Australia, Persian Gulf, shallow water	[11]

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